

**DISKRET PARAMETRLI IKKINCHI TARTIBLI OPERATORLI
MATRITSANI CHEGARALANGANLIKKA TEKSHIRISH.****Mansurov Tolibjon Ziyodullo o'g'li**Buxoro davlat Pedagogika instituti
"Aniq fanlar" kafedrası o'qituvchisi.**Xolmurodov Behzod Botir o'g'li**Buxoro davlat Pedagogika instituti
"Aniq fanlar" kafedrası o'qituvchisi.

Annotsiya. Panjaradagi soni saqlanmaydigan zarrachalar sistemasiga mos keluvchi blok operatorli matritsalarining spektral xossalarni o'rganish bilan bog'liq masalalar statistik fizika, qattiq jismlar fizikasi, mexanika va gidrodinamikaning ko'plab sohalarida uchrab turadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan ushbu mavzu dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Annotation. Issues related to the study of the spectral properties of block-operator matrices corresponding to a system of particles whose number is not conserved in the lattice are found in many areas of statistical physics, solid-state physics, mechanics, and hydrodynamics. From this point of view, this topic is relevant.

Kalit so'zlar: Gilbert fazosi, Fok fazosi, skalyar ko'paytma, kompleks fazo, qo'shma operatorlar, o'z – o'ziga qo'shma operator.

Keywords: Gilbert space, Fok space, scalar product, complex space, additive operators, self – adjoint operator.

$H_0 := \mathbb{C}$ - bir o'lchamli kompleks fazo, $H_1 := L_2(\mathbb{T}^d)$ - \mathbb{T}^d da aniqlangan kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi, (umuman olganda, kompleks qiymatli) funksiyalar Gilbert fazosi bo'lsin. $H^{(2)}$ orqali H_0 va H_1 fazolarning to'g'ri yig'indisini belgilaymiz, ya'ni $H^{(2)} := H_0 \oplus H_1$ [1].

Odatda, $H^{(2)}$ Gilbert fazosiga Fok fazosining qirqilgan ikki zarrachali qism fazosi deyiladi. $H^{(2)}$ Gilbert fazosining ixtiyoriy f elementi $f = (f_0, f_1)$ kabi tasvirlanadi, bunda $f_0 \in H_0, f_1 \in H_1$ [1].

$f = (f_0, f_1) \in H^{(2)}$ elementning normasi

$$\|f\| = \sqrt{\|f_0\|_0^2 + \|f_1\|_1^2}$$

formula yordamida topiladi:

$$\|f_0\|_0 = |f_0|, \quad \|f_1\|_1 = \sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{T}^d} \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |f_1(t)|^2 dt.}$$

Ikkita $f = (f_0, f_1), g = (g_0, g_1) \in H^{(2)}$ elementlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi

$$(f, g) = (f_0, g_0)_0 + (f_1, g_1)_1$$

kabi topiladi:

$$(f_0, g_0)_0 = f_0 \cdot \overline{g_0}, \quad (f_1, g_1)_1 = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} f_1(t) \overline{g_1(t)} dt.$$

$H^{(2)}$ Gilbert fazosida quyidagi ikkinchi tartibli

$$A_2^{(s)} := \begin{pmatrix} \hat{A}_{00}^{(s)} & \hat{A}_{01} \\ \hat{A}_{01}^* & \hat{A}_{11}^{(s)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

operatorli matritsani qaraymiz, bu yerda

$$A_{ii}: H_i \rightarrow H_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \quad A_{01}: H_1 \rightarrow H_0$$

operatorlar quyidagicha aniqlangan:

$$\hat{A}_{00}^{(s)} f_0 = s \varepsilon f_0, \quad f_0 \in H_0;$$

$$\hat{A}_{01} f_1 = \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t) f_1(t) dt, \quad f_1 \in H_1;$$

$$\left(\hat{A}_{11}^{(s)} f_1 \right) (x) = (-s \varepsilon + u(x)) f_1(x), \quad f_1 \in H_1.$$

Bunda, $s = \pm, \varepsilon$ – haqiqiy son, $v(\cdot)$ va $u(\cdot)$ lar haqiqiy qiymatli uzluksiz funksiyalar, $\alpha > 0$ – esa “ta'sirlashuv parametri”, \hat{A}_{01}^* operator mos ravishda \hat{A}_{01} operatorga qo'shma operatorlar bo'lib, ular quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\hat{A}_{01}f_1, f_0) &= (f_1, f_0\hat{A}_{01}^*) \\
 (\hat{A}_{01}f_1, f_0) &= \left(\alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt, f_0 \right) = \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt, \bar{f}_0 = \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} \overline{\alpha v(t)f_0} f_1(t)dt = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} f_1(t)\overline{\alpha v(t)f_0}dt \\
 \hat{A}_{01}^* &= \alpha v(t)f_0 \\
 (\hat{A}_{01}^*f_0)(x) &= \alpha v(x)f_0, \quad f_0 \in H_0.
 \end{aligned}$$

1 – lemma. $H^{(2)}$ Gilbert fazosida (1) formula orqali ta'sir qiluvchi ikkinchi tartibli $A_2^{(s)}$ operatorli matritsa chiziqli, chegaralangan va o'z – o'ziga qo'shma operator bo'ladi [2].

$A_2^{(s)}$ operatorni chegaralanganlikka tekshiramiz. Buning uchun shunday $C > 0$ soni topilib, ixtiyoriy $f \in H$ uchun

$$\|A_2^{(s)}f\| \leq C\|f\|$$

tengsizlik bajarilishini ko'rsatamiz.

Buning uchun quyidagi munosabatlardan foydalanamiz:

$$\|f_0\|_0 = |f_0|, \|f_1\|_1^2 = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |f_1(t)|^2 dt, \|f\|^2 = \|f_0\|_0^2 + \|f_1\|_1^2;$$

$$\|A_2^{(s)}f\|^2 = \|(A_2^{(s)}f)_0\|_0^2 + \|(A_2^{(s)}f)_1\|_1^2;$$

$$\|(A_2^{(s)}f)_0\|_0^2 = |s\varepsilon f_0 + \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt|^2$$

$$\|(A_2^{(s)}f)_1\|_1^2 = \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |\alpha v(x)f_0 + (-s\varepsilon + u(x))f_1(x)|^2 dx,$$

$$\|A_2^{(s)}f\|^2 = \left| s\varepsilon f_0 + \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt \right|^2 +$$

$$+ \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |\alpha v(x)f_0 + (-s\varepsilon + u(x))f_1(x)|^2 dx.$$

So'ngra ikki haqiqiy qiymatli a_1 va a_2 sonlar uchun

$$|a_1 + a_2|^2 \leq 2|a_1|^2 + 2|a_2|^2$$

tengsizlikdan foydalanamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \|A_2^{(s)}f\|^2 &= \left| s\varepsilon f_0 + \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt \right|^2 + \\ &\int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |\alpha v(x)f_0 + (-s\varepsilon + u(x))f_1(x)|^2 dx \leq 2|s\varepsilon f_0|^2 + \\ &+ 2 \left| \alpha \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt \right|^2 + \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} (2|\alpha v(x)f_0|^2 + 2|(-s\varepsilon + u(x))f_1(x)|^2) dx = \\ &= 2|s|^2|\varepsilon|^2|f_0|^2 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left| \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt \right|^2 + \\ &+ \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} (2|\alpha|^2|v(x)|^2|f_0|^2 + 2|(-s\varepsilon + u(x))|^2|f_1(x)|^2) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Endi yuqoridagi munosabatlar uchun quyidagi Koshi – Bunyakovskiy tengsizligini qo'llaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int f(x)g(x)dx \right|^2 &\leq \int |f(x)|^2 dx \cdot \int |g(x)|^2 dx. \\ \|A_2^{(s)}f\|^2 &\leq 2|s|^2|\varepsilon|^2|f_0|^2 + 2|\alpha|^2 \left| \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} v(t)f_1(t)dt \right|^2 + \\ &+ 2|\alpha|^2|f_0|^2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |v(x)|^2 dx + 2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |(-s\varepsilon + u(x))|^2|f_1(x)|^2 dx \leq \\ &\leq 2|s|^2|\varepsilon|^2|f_0|^2 + 2|\alpha|^2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |v(t)|^2 dt \cdot \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |f_1(t)|^2 dt + \end{aligned}$$

$$+2|\alpha|^2|f_0|^2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |v(x)|^2 dx + 2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^d} |-s\varepsilon + u(x)|^2 |f_1(x)|^2 dx.$$

$|u(x)| \leq M$ munosabatdan foydalangan holda, quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| A_2^{(s)} f \right\|^2 &\leq 2|s|^2 |\varepsilon|^2 \|f_0\|_0^2 + 2|\alpha|^2 \|v\|^2 \|f_1\|_1^2 + \\ &+ 2|\alpha|^2 \|f_0\|_0^2 \|v\|^2 + 2(-s\varepsilon + M)^2 \|f_1\|_1^2 = \\ &= \|f_0\|_0^2 (2|s|^2 |\varepsilon|^2 + 2|\alpha|^2 \|v\|^2) + \|f_1\|_1^2 (2|\alpha|^2 \|v\|^2 + 2(-s\varepsilon + M)^2); \end{aligned}$$

Quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$$C^2 = \max\{(2|s|^2 |\varepsilon|^2 + 2|\alpha|^2 \|v\|^2); (2|\alpha|^2 \|v\|^2 + 2(-s\varepsilon + M)^2)\}.$$

U holda

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| A_2^{(s)} f \right\|^2 &\leq C^2 (\|f_0\|_0^2 + \|f_1\|_1^2) \Rightarrow \left\| A_2^{(s)} f \right\|^2 \leq C^2 \|f\|^2 \Rightarrow \\ &\left\| A_2^{(s)} f \right\| \leq C \|f\|. \end{aligned}$$

Demak, diskret parametrli ikkinchi tartibli operatorli matritsa $A_2^{(s)}$ chegaralangan operator ekan.

ADABIYOTLAR

1. Б. И. Бахронов. У., Б. Б. Холмуродов. У. Изучение спектра одной 3×3 -операторной матрицы с дискретным параметром //Наука, техника и образование. – 2021. – №. 2-2 (77). – С. 31-34.
2. Бахронов Б. И. У., Мансуров Т. З. У. Вычисление существенного спектра обобщенной модели Фридрикса в системе MAPLE //Наука, техника и образование. – 2021. – №. 2-2 (77). – С. 35-38.
3. Мансуров Т. З. У. Классификация видов самостоятельных работ учащихся на уроках математики по дидактическому признаку //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 1078-1084.
4. Мансуров Т. З. У. Психолого-дидактические условия развития речемыслительной деятельности учащихся в процессе обучения математике //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 1109-1115.

5. Мансуров Т. З. У. Самостоятельная работа на уроках математики это средство творческого развития учащихся //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 1116-1121.
6. Мансуров, Т. З. у. (2022). Целесообразные уровни самостоятельности. Science and Education, 3(6), 1129–1135.
7. Ражабова Г. С. Об одном применении критерия Вейля //Молодой ученый. – 2017. – №. 25. – С. 12-13.
8. Раджабова Г. С. СОБСТВЕННЫЕ ФУНКЦИИ ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО ОПЕРАТОРА РАНГА 2 //УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА. – С. 10.
9. Раджабова Г. С. ОЦЕНКИ ДЛЯ ОПРЕДЕЛИТЕЛЯ ФРЕДГОЛЬМА СООТВЕТСТВУЮЩЕЙ СЕМЕЙСТВА МОДЕЛЕЙ ФРИДРИХСА //УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА. – С. 12.
10. Ражабова Г. С. АЛЬ–ХОРЕЗМИ-ВЕЛИКИЙ МАТЕМАТИК И ОСНОВАТЕЛЬ АЛГОРИТМА: Ражабова Гулчехра Саломовна, преподаватель кафедры «Точные науки» Педагогического института при Бухарском государственном университете //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 2. – С. 74-80.
11. Ismatovna, Asadova Yulduz. "THE METHODS OF TEACHING, LEARNING TO INDEPENDENT WORK: MOODLE EXPERIENCE AT BUKHARA STATE PEDAGOGICAL INSTITUTE IN UZBEKISTAN, BUKHARA STATE PEDAGOGICAL INSTITUTE." Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal 3.11 (2022): 1285-1291.
12. Ismatovna A. Y. METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS BASED ON ELECTRONIC PLATFORMS //Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Discoveries and Humanities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 119-125.
13. Ismatovna A. Y. Technology of organizing independent education of students in teaching" information technologies in education" on the base of distance

learning platforms //Studies in Economics and Education in the Modern World. –
2022. – T. 1. – №. 8.